

Start communication with

- Security guard
- Administrator
- Triage nurse
- Nurse at observation station
- Nurse at chronic room
- Clinical nurse/doctor
- Lab test
- Pharmacist

Communication at lab test room

Hi,
I am Deaf.
This app is helping us to communicate.

Press the button to continue the communication

OK

Communication at lab test room

Communication process

Please plan what you would like to communicate with the patient.

- Explain the medical test(s) to be done.
- Direct the patient to the next step.

Hand the phone back to the patient. Then press the button below to continue the communication.

OK

Communication at lab test room

Communication process

Please plan what you would like to communicate with the patient.

- Explain the medical test(s) to be done.
- Direct the patient to the next step.

Hand the phone back to the patient. Then press the button below to continue the communication.

OK

Communication at lab test room

Communication process

The nurse wants to examine you as follows...

OK

Communication at lab test room

Communication process

Please direct the patient to the next healthcare personnel.

- Pharmacist
- Administrator
- Triage nurse
- Nurse at the observation station
- Nurse at the chronic room
- Doctor/clinical nurse

Hand the phone back to the patient. Then press the button below to end the communication.

OK